

The Place and Effects of Information Management in Corporate Identity

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II. CONCEPT OF CORPORATE IDENTITY

Abstract—Corporate identity, which has several advantages such that the employees become integrated with their corporations, corporation is distinguished from its competitors and it is recognized by the masses, is the total of the distinctive corporate features that and corporation has. That the information takes part in production as a more important component than labor and capital has required that the corporations are reorganized as information-based. Therefore, information and its management have reached a basic and prevalent position in having sustainable competitive advantage. Thanks to the information management which regulates the information and makes it reachable and available, information will be produced in line with a specific purpose in the corporations and be used in all the corporate processes. As an auxiliary power for increase in the economic potential, efficiency and productivity of the corporation, corporate identity consists of four components. These are corporate philosophy, corporate design, corporate behavior and corporate communication. In this study, the effects of the information management on corporate identity are discussed from the point of these four elements.

Keywords—Corporate identity, information management.

I. INTRODUCTION

AS WELL AS the tangible and financial assets they have, the corporations which can manage also their information assets effectively, get the opportunities of existing and competitiveness. Nowadays, information increases incrementally and correspondingly it has been seen that the competitive capacity depends on the acquisition of the information and use of it correctly and appropriately. As its importance increases, information becoming strategic is considered as one of the production components in the information-based economic structure of today. With information management, the purpose of which is to develop methods in order to share the corporate information and use it effectively, the corporations which can spread the information they have to the whole organization and provide the employees with the information they need in the right place at the right time will achieve to prevent possible errors and losses.

From the components that affect corporate identity, thanks to information management, corporations will be able to manage the internal and external information flow in line with their own targets and will become different from their competitors with their identities being reinforced by the help of their corporate information. This research has the characteristics of a theoretical study including the concepts of corporate identity and information management.

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Identity is a concept representing the real personality of an corporation, reflecting it and comprising the symbols, images, communications, and behaviors that it uses for expressing itself. Corporate identity comprises those characteristics of an organization that its members believe are central, distinctive and enduring. That is, corporate identity consists of those attributes that members feel are fundamental to central and uniquely descriptive of distinctive the organization and that persist within the organization over time enduring [12]. The corporate identity is a manner of presentation of a corporation it's strategically planned and introduced corporate entity on the basis of the desired corporate image [1].

Corporate identity is how the corporate is presented to various audiences, being related to how its members perceive and seeing the organization [9]. Corporate identity is the planned and unplanned formation of cues by which stakeholders can recognize and identify an organization [2]. It also involves the whole of relatively abstract elements such as color, logo, typeface used on logo and the behaviors, culture, values, mission of the corporation and the style of communications which it uses and its relationships with various people and corporations [6].

Corporate identity is the set of meanings by which organization allows itself to be known and through which it allows people to describe, remember and relate to it. It is the way the organization chooses to present itself to its relevant target audiences by means of symbolism, communications and behavior. Corporate identity is what the company is, what it does and how it does it. It relates to the products and brands a company offers, how they are distributed, how the company communicates with publics or stakeholders, and how the company behaves [15]. If an organization is unclear about its identity, then it will not be able to assess its image as perceived by the different stakeholders, nor how these perceptions should be prioritized in terms of strategic planning, policy and practice [23].

The corporate communications, which is defined as the visualised form of the corporate identity, should be based on the core elements of the corporate identity and be consistent with them [15]. The purpose of the corporate identity management is to find the most suitable image for a corporation and convey messages related to this image [6].

The corporate identity which is biographical information and values of an organization is revealed through the corporate communications policies. Corporations identify their strategies so as to adapt to outside and solve internal integration problems. The strategic communications policies include the long-term view of how the corporation is evaluated by its

customers [14], [19]. For a successful corporate identity study, everything the organization does, and all the material the company uses, should be an integral part of the effort to convey a homogeneous and consistent identity. Corporate symbolism or corporate design, more specifically a consistent house style on business cards, letter heads, vehicles, gifts, clothes, equipment, packaging, etc., is an integral part of the corporate identity, or at least of the way in which it is made visible [15].

As activities conducted in order to diversify the organization's situation and position before its stakeholders, the corporate communication is a factor that makes a corporation different from others. Therefore, it is vital that this factor is managed, directed and controlled in line with the corporate targets. Corporate should be considered as not only the visual and physical presentation of the corporation but also a whole with corporate philosophy, corporate design, corporate behavior and corporate communication.

- a. Corporate philosophy: As its principle opinions about itself and the core element of the corporate identity, corporate philosophy includes the main values that create a corporate culture of an organization and assumptions [24].
- b. Corporate design: Corporate design is the process of selecting a structure for the tasks, responsibilities, and authority relationships within an organization [4]. For an organization, design is a tool for indicating its identity, increasing its visibility and its attraction, and thus promoting its sales and services [13]. Therefore organizational design is the way managers structure their organization to reach the organization's goals. The allocation of duties, tasks, and responsibilities among departments and individuals is a corporate design element [8].

Since products from different organization resemble each other technically and materially and since a head start in these areas can be quickly overcome, an organization must gain its competitive edge by other channels [13]. The corporate design of an organization reflects its efforts to respond to changes, integrate new elements, ensure collaboration, and allow flexibility [5]. Corporate design's goals are to get information to the right places for effective decision making, to help coordinate the organization's interdependent parts [8]. For this reason a corporate design plays a critical role in the success of an organization [4].

- c. Corporate behavior: Corporate behavior is the understanding, prediction, and management of human behavior in organizations [7]. In this respect corporate behavior is an interdisciplinary field dedicated to the study of human attitudes, behavior, and performance in organizations [17]. And also it is the study of what people think, feel, and do in and around organizations. Its focus is on employee behavior, decisions, perceptions, and emotional responses. It looks at how individuals and teams in organizations relate to each other and to their counterparts in other organizations [22].

The concepts and principles of corporate behavior are important because in every organization human beings ultimately make the decisions that control how the organization acquires and uses resources. Those people may cooperate with, compete with, support, or undermine one another. Their beliefs and feelings about themselves, their coworkers, and the corporate structure what they do and how well they do it. By understanding what causes people to behave as they do, positive outcomes will be achieved [17].

- d. Corporate communication: Communication is the process of people sharing thoughts, ideas, and feelings with each other in commonly understandable ways [3]. In this process, in order to achieve the desired results and influence the behaviors, the understandings are provided with verbal and non-verbal means. The transmission of understandings and meanings occurs via symbols and individuals employ these symbols to establish the understandings and meanings which they desire in their environments and interpret them [20]. Corporations that have corporate features and are a part of the social structure with their features lead a life in an order of relationships. A mandatory element in carrying on the corporate activities, communication is an important factor in providing corporate success and general competitive advantage [19]. Accordingly, with communication, it is assured that the corporate plans are applied and carried on the corporate activities; these are transferred to the employees, motivation of the employees is increased and plans are implemented wishfully.

Communication is a systematic and social process in which people interact with each other through symbols, create meanings and interpret them [20]. Corporate communication, useful and necessary in realizing the corporate objectives, is a matter of fact that includes actual communication activities. Corporate communication that demands an integrated approach to communications management is a total communication activity generated in order that a corporation achieve its planned aims. Corporate communication is an integrated approach aiming at establishing and maintaining the link between strategic objectives, the corporate identity and the corporate image in line with the communication activities of all functional departments. An integrated approach includes all relevant target groups and each unit of communication signs the corporate identity and emphasizes it [9], [15], [12].

III. CONCEPT OF INFORMATION MANAGEMENT

Information management is the collection of processes that rule the creation, dissemination and utilization of information and information works. It involves creation of supportive corporate structures, helping members, using technological instruments and diffusion of knowledge into corporation. In other words information management is an umbrella term that comprises a range of corporate processes and practices whose common feature is their concern with generating value from knowledge [18]. Then information management's purpose is enhancing corporate performance by explicitly designing and implementing tools, processes, systems, structures, and

cultures to improve the creation, sharing, and use of all kinds of knowledge that are critical for business performance and progress [16]. Eventually finally the real value of information management is providing a single overall view of the multiplicity of information development, information transfer and information utilization activities that occur within the organization and explicitly recognizing their commonalities and differences [18].

The purpose of the information management is to determine the critical corporate information, get it, then share stored information and apply it to right situations also determine the effectiveness of the information used in the application and in addition to these, make the necessary arrangements so as to increase the effectiveness of the information[11]. Thus, the intellectual capital corporation has, will be evaluated in the best way and a high level efficiency will be obtained from them, being used the information assets effectively. In this way, it will be possible to make use of information potential the corporation has. It will be possible to get access to corporate information when information is sagaciously organized and at right time, right people are enabled to use this information and it will be able to assured the production of new information from the information sources.

IV. THE PLACE AND EFFECTS OF INFORMATION MANAGEMENT IN TERMS OF CORPORATE IDENTITY

Information management covers any intentional and systematic process or practice of acquiring, capturing, sharing, and using productive information, wherever it resides, to enhance learning and performance in organizations. These investments in the creation of corporate capability aim at supporting the identification, documentation, memorization, and circulation of the cognitive resources, learning capacities, and competencies that individuals and communities generate and use in their professional contexts [25]. This process increases the competitive power of the corporation, providing it with several advantages such as originality and differentiation. Hence, it seems that availability and competitiveness is possible with the understanding of the information management for today's organizations. For contemporary organizations, corporate identity is one of the important competition elements. The key issue of corporate identity management is its role in achieving overall strategic aims of organization. All its features, which are the whole of an corporation's behaviors it adopts so as to represent itself and make itself different others, form the identity of an corporation. The aim of a corporate identity plan is to determine and communicate a corporate identity to meet these future strategic objectives [6]. Corporate philosophy, corporate design, corporate behavior and corporate communication are four major components that create the corporate identity. The effects of the information management on the corporate identity can discussed from the point of these four elements.

Today's economy that necessitates an innovative structure constantly forces corporations to change. The corporations which are able to manage the corporate information well they have, are able to use information as a basic factor in having a

competition advantage. Forming the most important part of the corporate identity, the corporate philosophy takes shape in line with the targets and objectives of the corporation. Corporate philosophy has ultimate aim to leverage maximum added value from the information resources [21]. Thereby the evaluation of the corporate philosophy with the understanding of information management provides the corporations with opportunities of competitive edge, career and strengthening their market presence. Moreover, corporate information will be able to use in order to improve new product or service and hereby, it gets easy to get the market. On the other hand for effective information management corporate culture needs to support integrated and collaborative working, pooling knowledge and information within the organization [21].

The second component forming the corporate identity is the corporate design and corporate structure is the sum of the ways an organization divides its labor into distinct tasks and then coordinates them. The structure provides the blueprint for the reporting relationships, controls, authority and decision making within an organization. Corporate design is the process of assessing the organization's strategy and environmental demands and determining the appropriate corporate structure. The base of an organization's structure and design includes people and activities [10]. For information to flow freely through an organization and for knowledge to be shared, the structure of the organization needs to be flexible, less hierarchical, less formal and less controlling [21]. So corporate design can be a chance for organizations about being different from their competitors and sticking in people's mind. The way of getting all these advantages at corporate level has seemed possible with reorganize all structure of belonging to the corporation in accordance with information management approach.

The other component of corporate identity is corporate behavior formed by reactions to possible events inside or outside the organization and it is encompasses the study of how organizations interact with their external environments, particularly in the context of employee behavior and decisions [22]. Information management has focused on making information needed accessible and available at relevant place and when needed. Accordingly, organization will be able to reach the information that it will needs so that it can immediately react to changes in the internal and external environment thanks to the understanding of the information management.

Corporate communication is the last component of the corporate identity. Gradually increasing need for information forming the basis of corporate and personal decisions makes the comprehension, comment and recognition of information masses almost impossible. Therefore, it is possible to say that both creating a good flow of communication with internal target groups and using the necessary information as required and on request, checking internal communication channels depend on only the management of corporate information effectively. In addition, the information management is considerable important for the corporations with regards to make individual and corporate training and learning process

easy as it is possible to make internal information sharing and transfer of experiences real with interpersonal communication interaction.

V. CONCLUSION

For 21th century's corporations, achievement is possible only with high competitive power, response speed and being a leading in the market. Getting a strategic advantage requires a new type of corporation has a structure which produces strategic information in way that will maximizes the corporate competitiveness and the success. Contrary to past, in today's business world which is fast, high technology product and global corporations have to obtain information, manage it and then use it so as to increase productivity, render a better service, maintain the corporate competitive and make continuously progress. Information management is an umbrella term that comprises a range of corporate processes and practices whose common feature is their concern with generating value from information [18]. Therefore, information management is an important and inevitable situation for the organizations which want to manage their corporate information in a best way. Corporate identity is in a condition of an important phenomenon affecting the preferences of the target groups. On the other part, by virtue of the fact that communication becomes widespread, corporations getting in contact with large masses are obliged to meet the needs of customers who buy their products and get their services, their employees, organizations which they cooperate with, and social and financial environments. For this reason, corporate identity, closely related to the activity styles of the organizations and strategies that they adopt, has become one of the indispensable concepts for the contemporary corporations of today.

Coordination of functioning of a corporation with the understanding of the information management will make many positive contributions to the corporation. The corporations adopting the information management will determine their corporate philosophy as the best evaluation instrument for their information sources they have, and provide a strategic competitive advantage to their competitors. In line with the understanding of information management, the corporation creates ideally the aspect of the corporation facing to society. Moreover, these corporations will be able to exhibit fast and right attitudes toward events that might happen in or outside the corporation and finally they will be able to provide their target groups with exact information just in time, implementing the internal and external corporate information communications.

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